

STRATEGIC APPROACH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *The article studies the strategic approach to the digital economy in our country, the complex issues of its effective implementation using the methods of theoretical observation and the index approach. Based on foreign practice, index indicators of the development of the digital economy are analyzed, conclusions and suggestions are given.*

Keywords: *Menedjery, upravlenie, globalization, digitization, strategy, income, economy, index.*

Introduction According to the World Bank, 66% of the world's wealth - 365 trillion US dollars - is created on the basis of human capital, and the reflection of intelligence and science takes place in the digital world.

The development and implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" program in Uzbekistan, first of all, the formation of thorough and perfect organizational and legal mechanisms, in addition, ensuring the harmonious cooperation of state bodies and business entities on the introduction of innovative ideas, technologies and developments, all spheres and Covering production and service in networks with digital technologies, training intellectually capable personnel with deep understanding of modern knowledge in this regard will serve to create an environment of "informed society" in the country.

Relevance of the research topic. As stated by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, **"Of course, we know very well that building a digital economy requires the necessary infrastructure, a lot of money and labor resources. However, no matter how hard it is, if we don't start today, when will we?! Tomorrow will be too late. Therefore, active transition to the digital economy will be one of our top priorities in the next 5 years."** According to international practice, the share of the digital economy in the gross domestic product is accepted as one of the indicators of development in this country. If we look at this indicator, we can see that these indicators are higher in developed countries compared to our country. Fig. 1

The share of the digital economy in the gross domestic product, %

Although there are sufficient opportunities and conditions for the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan, there are the following factors that negatively affect its acceleration;

- low internet speed and quality,
- existence of monopolies in digital business,
- information technology legislation is behind the times,
- low level of computer literacy,
- lack of professional specialists in the field of information technologies,
- insufficient provision of information technology cyber security.

That is why the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020 No. PF-6079 "On the approval of the strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" and measures for its effective implementation" It is planned to create all necessary conditions for solving strategic tasks, such as increasing its competitiveness.

The level of study of the topic. The term "Digital Economy" was introduced into scientific practice for the first time through the monograph "Information Age: Economy, Society and Culture" published by the Spanish and American sociologist, researcher Manuel Castels. However, until now, its theoretical aspects have been interpreted differently. For example, "Post-industrial economy" by D. Bell, "Information economy" according to O. Toffler, "Mega-economy" by V. Kuvaldin, "Economy based on information and communication" by I. Niiniluto, B. Gates "Techno-economy or digital economy", D. Tapscott promotes the ideas of the "Knowledge-Based Economy".

In Uzbekistan, "Conceptual and practical issues of the digital economy" were discussed by academician I. Iskandarov, Q. Abdurakhmanov, S. Gulomov and others. has been extensively studied by

Research methodology. In the course of the research, the strategic approach to digitalization in our country, comprehensive issues of its effective implementation were studied through theoretical

observation and systematic approach methods. Relying on foreign practice, we have analyzed index indicators for the development of the digital economy and expressed some opinions within this article.

Analysis results. The international ratings for evaluating the development of information technologies in the country include the following indexes that take into account several parameters at the same time, reflecting the state of development of the region.

Figure 2

Indicators of the status of Uzbekistan in international rankings

The following indicators in the international ratings evaluating the level of development of information technologies in the country are important.

1. The share of the digital economy in the gross domestic product,

In Uzbekistan, the share of the digital economy in the country's gross domestic product can be seen in the table below.

Figure 3

The share of the digital economy in the country's gross domestic product in Uzbekistan

1. The volume of investments in the digital economy in Uzbekistan.

Fig. 4

Investments in the digital economy in Uzbekistan, trillion soums

1. In the field of ICT, the speed of the Internet, its coverage of the territory of our country and its ease of use for the population,

Figure 5

High-speed internet coverage of the republic's territories, %

1. According to the latest data of our country's analysts, the number of Internet users in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which has more than 35 million inhabitants, has exceeded 27.2 million. Currently, 95 percent of the population's settlements are covered by mobile Internet, and 54 percent of households have access to high-speed Internet.

The level of development of e-commerce,

Fig. 5

Internet stores operating in Uzbekistan, one

2. The share of public services in the electronic government system,

In 2017, Uzbekistan launched a new version of the Single interactive state services portal (Single portal, DPI - my.gov.uz), which is a single electronic platform. Citizens and entrepreneurs can get government services and necessary information about them.

Figure 6

Percentage of public services provided in electronic format in Uzbekistan

Currently, the number of services provided at YaDEXKP has reached more than 300 in 20 directions.

2. Provision of organizations with experts.

Today, 100 schools specializing in information technologies are operating in Uzbekistan. In the next two years, it is planned to supply 205 such institutions and train more than 30 thousand students.

Conclusions and proposals. We believe that the following proposals should be implemented in order to develop the digital economy in our country and expand its reach.

- increasing the speed and quality of the Internet, taking into account the user group,

- ending existing monopolies by creating new models in digital business,
- organizing and conducting activities aimed at increasing the level of computer literacy knowledge in each region,
- attraction of foreign professionals in the field of information technologies,
- implementation of measures to increase cyber security of information technologies.

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